

SUYAKLAR SINISHINING TURLARI

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Annotation; Ushbu maqolada sinish - suyak yaxlitligining buzilishi, To'la sinish va suyak bo'lak bo'lib singandagi yoki darz ketgandagi kabi chala sinish haqida ilmiy izlanishlar olib borilgan.

Tayanch iboralar;deformatsiya,krepatitsiya,shish,ogriq,suyak chiqishi

Ochiq sinishda jarohat mavjud bo'ladi. U qo'l yoki oyoqqa suyak sinishiga olib keladigan haddan tashqari nagruzka berilganda sodir bo'ladi. Singan suyak uchi terini yirtib, tashqariga chiqib qoladi yoki bironta buyum teri qoplamni teshib o'tib, suyakni sindiradi. Taxmin qilingan siniq atrofidagi yumshoq to'qimaning har qanday zararlanishi ochiq sinishdan darak beradi. Yopiq sinishda teri qoplami zararlanmay qoladi-ki, sinishning bunday turi ko'proq uchraydi. Ochiq sinish nisbatan xavfli, chunki unda jarohatga infeksiya tushirish yoki qon yo'qotish xavfi mavjud bo'ladi.

Son suyagining sinishi oyoqning o'ziga xos deformatsiyasiga olib keladi. Shikastlangan oyoq sog'iga qaraganda kaltaroq ko'rinadi va tashqariga ag'darilgan bo'lishi mumkin.

Chiqish - suyakning bo'g'imdagi o'z normal holatiga nisbatan siljishidir. Chiqish, odatda, katta kuch ta'siri ostida ro'y beradi.(13.5rasm)

Suyak boshchasi o'zining normal holatidan tashqari chiqsa, boylamlar cho'ziladi yoki uziladi. Chiqishga sabab bo'lgan kuch ta'sirida suyak sinishi hamda yaqin atrofdagi nervlar va qon tomirlari zararlanishi mumkin. Chiqishni bo'g'imlar shaklining ko'zga tashlanadigan darajada buzilishiga qarab aniqlasa bo'ladi.

Boylamlarning cho'zilishi va uzilishi Suyak odatiy harakat amplitudasidan tashqari chiqqanda boylam cho'ziladi. Bo'g'inga haddan tashqari og'ir yuk tushishi boylamlarning to'la uzilishiga hamda suyak chiqishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Bunday hollarda suyak sinishi ham mumkin.

Boylamlar engil cho'zilganda, odatda, tez tuzalib ketadi. Jabrlanuvchi qisqa vaqt og'riq sezib yurishi mumkin, biroq tezda bir oz og'riq his qilgan holda yoki umuman og'riq his qilmay jismoniy faollikni yangidan boshlab yuborishi mumkin.

Shuning uchun kishilar bunday hodisalarga ko`pincha e'tibor berishmaydi, natijada bo`g`im qayta shikastlanishi mumkin. Boylamlar cho`zilishining og`ir shaklida bo`g`im sal harakatga kelsa, qattiq og`riq sezadi. To`piq va tizza bo`g`imlari, barmoqlar va bilak boylamlari cho`zilishi ko`p uchraydi.

Ba'zan boylamlarning cho`zilishi sinishga qaraganda jiddiyroq funktsional oqibatlar keltirib chiqarishi mumkin. Singandan keyin bitgan suyak kamdan-kam hollarda qayta sinadi. Bo`g`im esa, boylamlar cho`zilganidan yoki uzilganidan keyin, ancha beqaror (o`ynoqi) bo`lib qolishi mumkin. Bu hol qayta shikastlanish ehtimolini oshiradi.

Muskullar spazmasi (tortishishi)

Muskullar spazmasini shikastlanishga yo`yib bo`lmasa-da, u og`ir jismoniy ishni bajarishda yoki oyoq - qo`l uzoq vaqt davomida bir xil holatda turganida yuzaga keladigan og`riq turidir. Odatda, shu joyni cho`zish (uzatish) hamda uqalab yuborish, dam olish, shuningdek holatni o`zgartirish og`riq bartaraf etilishi uchun yetarli hisoblanadi. Qizib ketish natijasida muskulga yuk ko`p tushishi tufayli sodir bo`ladigan tortishish muskul spazmasini eslatishi mumkin, lekin u issiqda jismoniy mashqlarni bajarish jarayonida muskullar suyuqlik yo`qotishi natijasida ham sodir bo`lishi mumkin.

Tayanch-harakat apparati shikastlanishining belgilari quyidagilardan iborat: • og`riq, • shish, • odatdagi harakatlarni bajara olmaslik, • teri rangining o`zgarishi, • deformatsiya (shakl o`zgarishi), • tashqi qon ketishi, • shikast yetgan paytda suyaklarda qisirlagan yoki shaqillagan tovushning eshitilishi.

Ozmi-ko`pmi jiddiy shikastlanishda og`riq, shish bo`ladi va o`sha joyga tekkanda og`riydi.

Deformatsiyada shish, g`ayrioddiy g`adir-budurlik, bo`rtiq, chuqurcha paydo bo`ladi, tananing ma'lum qismi g`ayrioddiy burchak ostida ko`rinadi. Tananing shikastlangan va sog` qismlarini solishtirib deformatsiyani oson aniqlab olish mumkin. Jabrlanuvchining o`zi tanasining qaysi qismi qimirlamasligini yoki qanaqa harakat og`riq paydo qilayotganini aytishi mumkin.

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